

0.989**) between SPAD-501 reading and chlorophyll content (see figure). The instrument manufacturer obtained a correlation of 0.815 between chlorophyll reading and actual chlorophyll content

using data from several crop species. SPAD-501 is reliable in determining relative chlorophyll content as an index of cold tolerance.

This method has considerable

potential in quantifying leaf discoloration due to low temperature as well as yellowing caused by other stresses such as nutrient deficiency, diseases, and drought. *J*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Response of rice varieties to protective irrigation

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Extended breaks in monsoon rainfall significantly reduce yield of rice grown on lateritic soils with high infiltration, medium to high total N, high K, and low P in Konkan, India. Yield losses are greatest on newly developed, terraced uplands. Protective irrigation may reduce those losses.

We evaluated 135-d Jaya and RP4-14 for response to protective irrigation in a factorial randomized block design with 5 replications on newly developed terraces of lateritic soil. Rice was sown 9 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 5 Sep at 3 seedlings/hill and 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plots received 50-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha at transplanting and 50 kg N in 2 equal splits at 1-mo intervals. Plots received 251.84 mm of water at each protective

Influence of protective irrigation on grain and straw yield, Maharashtra, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			
	Control		Protective irrigation	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Jaya	2.9	3.1	3.9	4.1
RP4-14	3.1	3.1	3.9	4.0
Mean	3.0	3.4	3.9	4.0
		S. Em. ±	CD at 5%	
Variety:	Grain	0.1	ns	
	Straw	0.1	ns	
Irrigation:	Grain	0.1	0.4	
	Straw	0.1	0.3	
Interaction:	Grain	0.2	ns	
	Straw	0.1	0.4	

irrigation (13 Jul; 19, 21, 24, and 27 Sep; and 1 Oct). Recommended pest control measures were applied. Harvest was 25 Oct.

Yields were relatively low. Protective irrigation increased yield an average 30% over that of the control (see table). *J*

IET7613, a drought-resistant upland rice

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Improved short-duration, drought-

resistant, upland varieties are needed for the Uttar Pradesh plains, where rainy season seldom lasts more than 90 d. Newly developed IET7613 (M63-83/Cauvery) yields 15% more at low to moderate soil fertility than locally grown N22. IET7613 is a semidwarf, drought-resistant upland rice that matures in 85 d.

Rainfall distribution in Faizabad, India, during upland trials in 1982-84.

Six All India Coordinated Rice-Improvement Project upland trials from 1982 to 1984 at Faizabad compared IET7613 with N22. Soil was a sandy loam with 57% sand, 27% silt, and 14% clay. Field capacity and permanent wilting coefficient of the 0-15 cm soil profile were 22.5 and 4.6% with bulk density 1.42 g/cm³. After rains had softened the soil, it was tilled and 100 kg seed/ha was drilled 4-5 cm deep in open furrows at 20-cm spacing and covered with soil. Fields were sown the 1st wk of July, except for 1 yr, when sowing was in the 1st wk of August. The crop received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha and a foliar spray of Zn sulfate 2 wk after germination. Weeding was by hand.

Average rainfall for the 3 seasons was 1268 mm but distribution was erratic (see figure). In 1982, a 10-d dry spell occurred at seedling stage and rains almost stopped after 14 Sep. In 1983, there were 15-d dry spells in mid-July and August and rain stopped on 13 Oct. In 1984, rainfall exceeded 400 mm the 2d wk, there were dry periods in August, and rains stopped in mid-September.

IET7613 performed better than N22 because it has greater sink potential, higher nutrient use efficiency, and better drought resistance (see table). *ℓ*

Characters of improved IET7613 and traditional N22 grown at Faizabad, India.

Character	N22	IET7613 ^a
Agronomic		
Duration (d)	85	85 n.s.
Height (cm)	104	86***
Leaf	Large groopy	Small erect
Maturity synchrony		
Between panicles	Synchronous	Synchronous
Within panicles	Acropetal uniform	Acropetal uniform
Grain type	Short bold	Long bold
Yield		
Panicles (no./m ²)	315	410 n.s.
Grain (no./panicle)	69	62***
1000-grain weight (g)	20	27***
Ripening (%)	78	81 n.s.
Yield (t/ha)	3.3	3.8***
Physiological		
Sink potential (g/panicle)	1.24	1.90***
Nutrient use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)	52	61***
Harvest index (%)	47	49 n.s.
Productivity (kg grain/d per ha)	39	45***
Spikelet sterility (%)	22	19 n.s.
Seed dormancy (fresh harvest)	Present	Absent
Lodging	Susceptible	Resistant
Root growth	Abundant thick	Abundant thick
Root penetration	Strongly geotropic	Moderately geotropic
Drought response		
Leaf water potential (-bar)	19	21***
Relative water content (%)	66	64***
Leaf rolling (score)	5 (complete rolling)	3 (partial rolling)**
Drought sustenance (d)	9.1	10.4**
Panicle exertion	Well exerted	Moderately well exerted**
Stem extension growth	Very slow	Almost ceases
Drought injury	2	3 n.s.
Post-drought recovery score	2 (slow)	1 (fast) n.s.

^a***significant at P = 0.001, ** significant at P = 0.01, n.s. (not significant).

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Varietal evaluation of rice genotypes in coastal saline soil

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The IRSATON screening set (61 entries) from IRTP was evaluated for salinity tolerance and grain yield along with local checks CSRI, CSR3, and CSR6. The seeds of 64 genotypes were sown on 13 Jul and transplanted on 17 Aug 1983 in randomized block design with 3 replications. Each entry was transplanted in 3 rows of 20 hills each; row and plant spacing was 25 cm. N at 70 kg/ha was in 2 splits. In situ soil

salinity ranged from 7.5 to 8.4 dS/m at transplanting and 5.8 to 10.1 dS/m at flowering. Data on agronomic attributes were collected from five plants selected at random in each replication, and survival rate at maturity was determined. Data on quantitative characters of 25 genotypes whose tolerance scores at the vegetative stage, at maturity, or at both stages ranged from moderate (4 to 5) to excellent (3) are given in the table.

CSR1, CSR3, and CSR6 were scored highly tolerant at vegetative and maturity stages. CSR1 grain yield was highest (1.4 kg/plot), followed closely by that of CSR3 (1.3 kg/plot) and CSR6 (1.28 kg/plot). Spikelet sterility, which is

highly affected by soil salinity, averaged 22%; the maximum was 31% in CSR6 and the lowest was 14% in CSR3. Plant survival at maturity was 98%. Other genotypes rated highly tolerant with similar spikelet sterility and plant survival were, in order of merit, C14-1, IR4630-22-2-5-1-3, and IR4422-6-2. Their lower yield may be due to their lower yield potential.

IR4630-22-2-17 had a salinity tolerance score of 3 at the vegetative stage, but was scored 4 at maturity. Its spikelet sterility of 18% was the second lowest of the entries. With 97% plant survival and low spikelet sterility, IR4630-22-2-17 appeared highly promising.